

Rolling-out pioneering carbon dioxide capture and transport chains from inland European industrial facilities: a techno-economic, environmental, and regulatory evaluation

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7. Supplementary data

7.1. Environmental impacts of pioneering chains

While the goal of CCTS chains is the reduction of global warming intensity of the industrial point sources, they unavoidably lead to other environmental impacts. Thus, 15 additional environmental impact categories are analysed besides GWI to quantify the extent of burden-shifting. For this purpose, the Environmental Footprint methods are used, version 3.0, to quantify the environmental impacts [1]. The environmental impacts for all pioneering chains shown in Fig. 1 include direct and indirect emissions (i.e., scope 1, 2 and 3).

In contrast to the functional units defined in Section 3.4, the environmental impacts are determined for 1 ton of CO₂ captured, conditioned and transported to the nearest harbour. Thereby, to enable a comparison between the four pioneering chains, each environmental impact is normalized to the corresponding impact of the chain from Niederurnen.

The Niederurnen chain has the highest environmental impact in 6 out of 16 categories, while it only achieves the lowest impact in one category. The impact categories where the Niederurnen chain achieves the highest impact

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Figure 1: LCA results for all pioneering chains including direct and indirect emissions (i.e., scope 1, 2 and 3) normalized by the impacts of the chain from Niederurnen. Thus, the Niederurnen chain has a value of 1 in each impact category. Note that "Eutrophication: Freshwater" and "Land use: Soil quality index" extend over the axis limits.

are dominated by the transportation step, accounting for more than 50% of the total impact in the respective categories. The high share in impacts of

the transportation step result from the distance between Niederurnen and the harbour in Rotterdam, which is more than twice as large as the distance for the other pioneering chains.

The HC Góraźdze chain has the largest environmental impact in 5 out of 16 impact categories. These impact categories are dominated by the utilities for the capture and conditioning step, contributing to more than 50% of the environmental impact. The Polish electricity grid mix depends heavily on the combustion of fossil fuels, such as coal, leading to a high environmental impact in many categories. In the category "*Eutrophication: Freshwater*", this is particularly evident with an impact nine times greater than the impact of the Niederurnen chain. In 2 out of 16 impact categories, the Góraźdze chain achieves the smallest environmental impact.

The chain from Skutskär shows the best performance in 7 of the 16 analysed impact categories. The Skutskär chain benefits from the Swedish electricity mix, mainly based on renewable and nuclear power and the fact that no transport step is required due to direct harbour access. However, the Skutskär chain has the largest impact in 4 categories. These impacts are mainly driven by the use of biomass boilers to generate the steam for the capture process and, in the case of the "*Ionising radiation: Human health*" impact category, by the large share of nuclear power in the Swedish electricity grid mix. Thereby, the impact on "*Land use: Soil quality index*" exceeds the impact of the Niederurnen chain by a factor of 4.

The chain from Hannover achieves the best performance in 6 of the 16 impact categories while having the largest impact in only one impact category. However, it should be noted that the "*Eutrophication: Freshwater*" impact is 5 times larger than for the Niederurnen chain. Similar to the Góraźdze chain, the impact can be attributed to the local electricity grid mix.

7.2. Network of feasible connections

Fig. 2 shows the network of feasible connections from KVA Linth to the harbor of Rotterdam considered in this work, i.e., based on existing transport technologies and following established connections (with the exception of truck transport which is possible at any location with road access). This network can be converted into a simple directed graph, which can subsequently be used to apply the Yen's algorithm to compute the K most economical pathways [2].

Figure 2: Network of feasible connections from KVA Linth to the harbor of Rotterdam.

7.3. Techno-economic analysis framework

8. Techno-economic analysis framework

8.1. Techno-economic analysis workflow

The workflow adopted for carrying out the techno-economic assessment is illustrated in Fig. 3, including the interactions with the life cycle assessment presented in Section 3.4.

8.2. Economic boundaries

This section specifies the main assumptions considered to perform the economic evaluations. All economic assessments are reported on a 2019 basis. In cases in which all costs are not directly available in 2019 prices, investment costs must be adjusted to the correct level of prices [3]. This will be preferably done using the DACE index for process installations in Germany, generated by the Dutch Association of Cost Engineers (DACE), which generates indices to indicate the change of actual prices in the Netherlands and outside the Netherlands.

When necessary, exchange rate are also be used to convert costs into Euro.

Figure 3: Workflow of the techno-economic analysis performed, including the interactions with the life cycle assessment.

Yearly average values for the DACE are given in Table 1, and exchange rates from key relevant currencies to Euro are given in Table 2.

Table 1: Yearly DACE indexes.

Year	DACE index
2015	100
2016	102
2017	105
2018	107
2019	103
2020	TBA

8.3. First-of-a-kind and Nth-of-a-kind

"FOAK" (First-of-a-kind) type of cost estimates reflect projects which have higher costs in the early stages of commercialization. With accumulated capacity and the associated accumulated experience, the costs of a project are reduced. Once the technology is mature, projects become "NOAK" (Nth-of-a-kind). The guidelines for FOAK and NOAK estimations are based on Roussanaly et al. [4], where a detailed justification of some of the choices can be found.

FOAK projects can lead to higher investment costs than NOAK due to a variety of reasons. Some typical reasons for the higher investment cost are:

Table 2: Average exchange rates for 2020.

Currency	1 €
Norwegian kroner (NOK)	10.7228
Swedish krona (SEK)	10.4848
Polish złoty (PLN)	4.4430
Swiss francs (CHF)	1.0705
US dollar (USD)	1.1422

- Sub-optimal and oversized design
- Additional construction costs due to retrofitting
- Higher margin from contractors to face the risk of cost overrun
- Delays in construction
- Additional safety measures
- Additional spare and redundant equipment
- Higher process contingencies
- Higher system contingencies
- Stricter material selection and design standards
- Higher escalation cost during planning and construction
- Higher discount rate to reflect risk premium
- Lower levelized capacity factor

While these additional costs can have a more significant impact on CO₂ capture and conditioning, also CO₂ transport may be impacted. Indeed, while CO₂ transport via pipeline is a quite mature technology, other system like train, trucks, barges, and ships can be less mature, resulting in higher investment costs due to similar factors such as sub-optimal design, additional construction costs due to retrofitting, higher margin from contractors to face the risk of cost overrun, delays in construction and additional safety measures.

Operating costs are impacted to a smaller extent but are also higher for FOAK projects than for NOAK projects. Reasons for higher fixed operational costs for FOAK projects are:

- Higher regulatory fees due to a higher regulatory cost exposure
- Higher professional services due to additional legal support in the form of supplier warranty management, claims management and overall commercial risk mitigation
- More tools and equipment required for maintenance
- Higher lease expenses because FOAK facilities are expected to operate for a shorter period of time and thus pay higher lease rates
- More training required, especially for unique FOAK technology, for technicians, plant operators and plant engineers
- Higher property taxes and insurance due to a lack of prior commercial experience.

In this work, the pioneering chains are evaluated with a FOAK, or near FOAK, approach, especially on the capture section. The rationale behind this choice is to reflect the expected cost of the implementation of such chains as early movers. However, the Skutskär chain is also evaluated with a NOAK approach in order to appreciate the impact of such assumption. Table 3 lists the factors that are changed, as well as their values, when applying a FOAK or NOAK approach.

8.4. Capital investment

A Bottom-Up approach (BUA) is used to estimate the total capital requirement of the CO₂ capture and conditioning process, while a Top-Down Approach (TDA) is adopted for the transport part of the pioneering chains.

8.4.1. Bottom-up approach

This approach is organized along the following steps:

- First, the direct cost of all relevant equipment of the considered process must be evaluated. It is worth noting that the direct cost is the sum of the Equipment Cost and the Installation Cost.
- The Total Direct Cost without process contingencies (TDC') is then calculated by summing up the direct cost of all units.

Table 3: Factors for FOAK and NOAK approach.

	FOAK	NOAK	Unit
General data			
Discount rate	10	8	%
Years of operation	20	25	y
From TDC to TPC			
Process contingency	20	10	%TDC'
System contingency	10	0	%TDC'
Indirect costs	25	15	%TDC
Project contingency	40	30	%EPC
From TPC to TCR			
Owner's costs	10	7	%TPC
Start-up - Modifications	3	2	%TPC
Start-up - Spare parts	0.5	0.5	%TPC
Start-up - Labour cost	6	3	mro*
Start-up - Maintenance, materials, chemicals and consumables	1	1	mro*
Start-up - Fuel	2.5	0.25	mro*
Interest over construction			
Allocation over years of construction			
Year -3	20	0	%
Year -2	30	40	%
Year -1	30	30	%
Year 0	20	30	%
Overnight factor	1.159	1.091	

*Months of regular operation

- The Total Direct Cost (TDC) with contingency is then calculated by adding the appropriate process contingency factor in order to reflect the technology maturity of the process considered. To be consistent with the maturity assumption implied by the FOAK cost basis, higher process contingencies than for a NOAK cost basis are considered. In particular, 20% for process contingencies is included for the pioneering chains. In addition, a system contingency factor of 10% is also included to reflect additional capital costs related to the integration of the CO₂ capture and conditioning process with the industrial plant. This cost is unique to initial installations of a new technology.
- The Engineering, Procurement and Construction costs (EPC) are then calculated by adding the indirect costs.
- The Total Plant Cost (TPC) is then calculated as the sum of EPC cost and project contingency estimated following the AACE 16R-90 guidelines. Considering the level of modelling detail, a project contingency cost of 40% is deemed appropriate.
- The Total Capital Requirement (TCR) is finally calculated as the sum of TPC, the owner costs, spare parts, modifications, interest during construction and the start-up cost. The owner cost, spare parts, modifications are set as percentages of the TPC (10, 0.5 and 3% respectively). The interest during construction is calculated, at the end of each subsequent year, assuming that the construction costs are shared over a 3.5-year construction period following a 20/30/30/20 allocation. Finally, the start-up costs are evaluated considering 6 months of maintenance, operating and support labour, 2 months of materials, chemicals, and consumables costs and 2.5 months of fuel costs

A geographic location factor, shown in Table 7 is also considered.

8.4.2. Top-down approach

A top-Down approach can be used to estimate the EPC of the plant, which is based on the following steps:

- The EPC is estimated directly, based on equipment supplier estimates of EPC costs for the entire plant. The cost estimates through this approach by equipment suppliers are typically based on current technology maturity and uncertainties.

Table 4: Process contingency factor at different levels of technology maturity.

Technology Status	Process Contingency Cost (% TDC without contingencies)
New concept with limited data	40+
Concept with bench-scale data	30-70
Small pilot plant data	20-35
Full-sized modules have been operated	5-20
Process is used commercially	0-10

Table 5: System contingency cost at different levels of technology maturity.

Technology Status	System Contingency Cost (% of total process capital for all newly integrated components)
First commercial scale project (FOAK)	0-20
Second or third commercial projects	0-10
Fourth and fifth commercial projects	0-5
All subsequent commercial projects	0

Table 6: Project contingency based on the AACE 16R-90 guidelines.

Estimate Class	Design effort	Project contingency cost (%-EPC)
Class I (similar to AACE Class 5/4)	Simplified	30-50
Class II (similar to AACE Class 3)	Preliminary	15-30
Class III (similar to AACE Class 3/2)	Detailed	10-20
Class IV (similar to AACE Class 1)	Finalised	5-10

Table 7: Geographic specific factors.

Location	Materials cost factor	Labour productivity factor	Labour cost factor
The Netherlands	1.00	1.00	1.00
Eastern Europe	0.92	1.28	0.40

- The TPC is then calculated as the sum of the EPC cost and project contingency estimated following the AACE 16R-90 guidelines reported in Table 6. Considering the level of modelling detail, a project contingency cost of 40% is deemed appropriate.
- The TCR is finally calculated following the same approach outlined for the BUA.

8.5. Operating costs

The annual average capacity factor (CF) of a plant reflects the fraction of product actually generated in a year relative to the maximum possible generation, i.e., for the same plant operated for a year at the full rated capacity. The higher the CF, the lower the cost per unit of product. While the CCTS chain is expected to operate to normal load after a few years, it is assumed that the first two years of operation will have operation levels reduced to account for ramping up of operation, because of technical issues, etc. Thus, during the first two years of operation, capacity factors of 40% and 65% are assumed, respectively, while industry-specific capacity factors (presented in Table 8) are considered afterwards.

Table 8: Industry-specific capacity factors.

Industry	Industry-specific capacity factor	Reference
Cement	91.3%	[4]
Waste to Energy	80.0%	Internal project communication
Pulp and paper	95.9%	[4]

8.5.1. *Maintenance, insurance and labour costs*

The fixed operating costs include maintenance, insurance, and labour costs, and are estimated as follows:

- Insurance and local property taxes: The total annual cost of insurance, local property taxes and miscellaneous regulatory and overhead fees is to be a total of 2% of TPC.
- Maintenance costs: Maintenance costs include costs of preventive maintenance, corrective maintenance (repair and replacement of failed components) and periodic replacement of materials. The maintenance costs correspond to 2% of the TPC excluding periodic replacement of materials which are defined based on the process. It is worth noting that the 2% considered for the maintenance costs also includes maintenance labour (which correspond to 40% of this 2%).
- Labour costs: Labour costs include operating labour, administrative and support labour. The operating labour costs are estimated based on the number of employees and a ‘fully burdened’ cost of labour, including social security payments that are in turn estimated based on the geographical location and considering a 5-shift pattern. When the information is not available, 60 k€/year per employee is to be assumed. This corresponds to the average of the Euro area (27 countries). Administrative and support labour costs are also included and are assumed to be equal to 30% of the operating and maintenance labour cost. Compared to a mature commercial technology, a FOAK facility can be expected to have significantly more equipment suppliers, contractors, consultants, and other personnel over an extended period of time. To account for this, the man-hour costs are increased 2 times compared to that of a commercial facility during the first three years of operation.

The labor cost levels are based on the Labour Cost Survey performed by Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union. The data relate to total average hourly labor costs and to the labor cost categories "wages and salaries" and "employers' social security contributions plus taxes paid minus subsidies received by the employer" [5].

8.5.2. *Utilities and consumables costs*

The variable operating costs include material utilities consumption such as electricity, natural gas, process water, and chemicals. The costs of the

Table 9: Labor cost levels for industry except construction (compensation of employees plus taxes minus subsidies).

Country	Annual labour costs in thousand Euro (k€/year)
Euro area (27 countries)	60
Sweden	86
Poland	22
Germany	87
Switzerland	60

main utilities and consumables are evaluated based on the process energy and mass balance and the costs presented in Table 2. Certain utilities such as electricity and steam can be obtained at different costs depending on the source, amount, and location.

The cost of electricity for industrial sites is based on the average National European electricity energy prices, see Table 3.

The cost of steam for industrial sites are specific to the heat supply strategy considered, see Table 2.

Finally, additional operating costs can also be expected in the first years of operation, especially for a demonstration project due to learning and training time, inefficiency, and so on. Utility consumption is therefore assumed to be 15% higher than the basis during the first three years of operation [6].

8.6. Project valuation

In order to the CO₂ avoidance cost, two project finance related characteristics are of importance: the discount rate and the project duration. Here, a real discount rate (i.e., without inflation) of 10% is considered in order to perform the project financial valuation. This is higher than commonly considered in NOAK type of estimates as FOAK projects lack prior operating experience, which results in a risk premium compared to the discount rate of a NOAK project. Similarly, a project economic lifetime of 20 years will be considered. This duration is shorter than the commonly used 25 years for NOAK estimates as FOAK project face significant long-term uncertainties (economic, political, etc.) related to the implementation of FOAK projects.

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